

PAPER TITLE

Physical Implications of Turbulence Anisotropy for Loss Generation in a Transonic Compressor Rotor Midspan Section

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OBJECTIVES

wall-resolved LES, transonic compressor rotor, turbulence anisotropy

BACKGROUND AND INTRODUCTION

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has become an essential tool in industrial applications. It enables the simulation of fluid flow, heat transfer, and related phenomena, allowing engineers to optimize designs, improve performance, enhance safety, and reduce costs through virtual prototyping [1, 2]. In turbomachinery, CFD capabilities have advanced considerably in recent years. In particular, three-dimensional Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) simulations are now routinely used to predict flow behavior in the complex geometries of compressors and turbines with good accuracy. A major factor in this progress

has been the reduction in turnaround time, made possible by improved hardware, software, and parallel computing. This has enabled faster design iterations and more efficient validation. At the same time, better turbulence and transition models have led to more reliable predictions, making CFD an indispensable part of both early design stages and the optimization of existing turbomachinery.

Nevertheless, future demands for higher efficiency and sustainability in turbomachinery design cannot be met by current RANS approaches alone. Meeting stricter energy efficiency standards and environmental regulations requires capturing flow phenomena that are more complex and sensitive to small design or operating changes. For example, achieving high efficiency in off-design conditions, improving energy recovery, and reducing emissions all depend on flow features that traditional RANS models cannot predict with sufficient accuracy. To design next-generation turbomachinery, turbulence models must be enhanced to better capture highly three-dimensional, unsteady flow structures such as separation, shock–boundary layer interactions in transonic and supersonic regimes, and complex secondary and duct flows [3]. Promising directions include higher-fidelity turbulence closures, improved near-wall treatments, and hybrid RANS–LES approaches. Only with such developments can CFD achieve the predictive accuracy needed to support the design of more efficient and sustainable turbomachinery.

Over the past decade, scale-resolving simulations have played a key role in advancing the understanding of turbulence in turbomachinery [4]. Unlike RANS methods, they can resolve unsteady flow structures and turbulence mechanisms directly, offering much deeper insight into secondary flows, loss mechanisms, and unsteady blade interactions. These insights form a strong basis for the development of more efficient and innovative turbomachinery designs. Although such simulations remain too expensive for routine use and can only be performed for selected operating points and designs, they provide highly valuable infor-

mation about the complex three-dimensional flow physics. Importantly, the data generated by these simulations can be used to improve turbulence and transition models [5].

One effective approach in this context is the analysis of turbulence anisotropy. Instead of only considering flow fields in physical space, anisotropy analysis highlights directional dependencies of the Reynolds stresses. This makes it possible to identify subtle features such as preferred energy transfer pathways or localized turbulent structures. Such information deepens the understanding of turbulence and provides essential input for the development of advanced turbulence closures and more accurate predictive models, leveraging AI- and ML-based frameworks.

In Fard Afshar et al. [6] a detailed assessment of turbulence anisotropy along a Low Pressure Turbine using the Reynolds stress anisotropy tensor and barycentric map is given. The analysis demonstrates the full range of turbulence states on the suction side midspan section, from near-wall one-component structures to complex transitions in the separated shear layer and passage flow, thereby offering new physical insight into the anisotropy dynamics of separation-induced boundary layer transition to turbulence. In contrast, it was shown that Linear Eddy Viscosity Model predictions remain nearly isotropic in the separation region, clearly underscoring their inability to capture these features. This discrepancy is identified as a key reason for the poor performance of RANS in predicting Mach number distribution and total pressure loss.

In this work, we use a similar approach to investigate the turbulence anisotropy of a transonic compressor stage at mid-span, as introduced in [7]. Numerical simulations of different fidelity are available, including wall-resolved LES [7, 8], hybrid RANS–LES [9], and both unsteady and steady RANS [10, 11]. The results are investigated in terms of their impact of anisotropy prediction accuracy on loss behavior.

METHODOLOGIES

The investigated test case is presented together with the numerical methods and physical models. The computational setup, including discretization, boundary conditions, and modeling assumptions, is described. Approaches for turbulence anisotropy and aerodynamic loss estimation are also outlined, providing the framework for the subsequent analysis and discussion.

Testcase & Methods

Transonic Compressor stage midspan section The initial configuration for the test case is a Q3D translational

framework with an extent of 20% chord in spanwise direction [7] derived from the Transonic Compressor Darmstadt (TCD) single-stage geometry as an open source test case available via the Global Power and Propulsion Society (GPPS) [12], cf. Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1: Derivation of Q3D translational setup

The feasibility of the Q3D extraction and its applicability was demonstrated in [7]. The flow conditions are summarized in table 1.

TABLE 1: TEST-CASE DETAILS AND INFLOW CONDITIONS.

Re_r	Re_s	Ma_r	Ma_s	Φ	Ψ	BPF
1×10^6	7×10^5	0.935	0.525	0.60	1.86	1.64

HiPSTAR-Solver The LES cases were performed using the high-order in-house compressible multi-block structured flow solver, HiPSTAR [13]. For the cases considered here fourth-order accurate spatial and temporal discretization was used with the Wall-Adaptive Local Eddy viscosity (WALE) subgrid scale model, [14]. A sliding interface method [15] was applied to enable full stage simulations. The fluid is modeled as a perfect gas with properties of cold air and the ratio of specific heats equal to 1.4. Inflow turbulence was generated using a compressible-flow extension of the digital filter approach of Klein et al. [16] resulting in turbulence intensity of $TU \approx 1.6\%$ at rotor leading edge. The meshing was carried out using an overset method [17] consisting of 3 O-grids around the airfoils (1x rotor, 2x stator) in front of Cartesian H-background grids in the rotor and stator domain (1.664×10^6 and 1.703×10^6 grid points in the midspan plane). For the rotor blade 768000 and the stator blades 320000 grid points each were used in the midspan plane. The span direction was discretized with 320 grid points, resulting in a total number of \approx

1.528×10^9 grid points. This results in the wall resolution in viscous coordinates $\Delta x^+ \leq 25$, $\Delta y^+ \leq 3$ and $\Delta z^+ \leq 25$. More details are given in [7, 8].

TRACE-Solver All hybrid RANS/LES and (u)RANS simulations have been carried out with DLR's in-house solver TRACE, which has continuously been developed at the Institute of Propulsion Technology in the Department for Numerical Methods [18]. Details with regard to the hybrid RANS/LES are given in [9] as well as for the (u)RANS in [7, 10].

Describing turbulence anisotropy

Any turbulence state can be expressed as a linear combination of three limiting cases: one-component (1C), isotropic two-component (2C), and isotropic three-component (3C) turbulence. The 3C state represents fully isotropic, "spherical" turbulence with zero anisotropy. The 2C state corresponds to two velocity components of equal strength, often described as "pancake-shaped" turbulence. In contrast, the 1C state is dominated by a single velocity component, for example in grid turbulence under axisymmetric expansion, and is referred to as "cigar-shaped" turbulence.

In practical engineering flows, turbulence is rarely isotropic. Boundaries and strong adverse pressure gradients typically lead to strongly anisotropic, non-equilibrium states. The degree of anisotropy can be quantified by the Reynolds stress anisotropy tensor a_{ij}

$$a_{ij} = \frac{\overline{u'_i u'_j}}{2k} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{3}, \quad k = \frac{\overline{u'_i u'_i}}{2} \quad (1)$$

where k is the turbulent kinetic energy and δ_{ij} the Kronecker delta. Lumley [19] and later Choi and Lumley [20] showed how turbulence states can be visualized using the invariants of a_{ij} and realizability constraints. Banerjee et al. [21] extended this approach by introducing a barycentric map, derived from the eigenvalues $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 > \lambda_3$ of a_{ij} . These eigenvalues define the weights C_{1C} , C_{2C} , and C_{3C} , which determine the contribution of each limiting state:

$$a_{ij} = C_{1C}a_{1C} + C_{2C}a_{2C} + C_{3C}a_{3C} \quad (2)$$

with

$$C_{1C} = \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \quad C_{2C} = 2(\lambda_2 - \lambda_3) \quad C_{3C} = 2\lambda_3 + 1. \quad (3)$$

To make anisotropy visualization more intuitive, Emory and Iaccarino [22] proposed a color mapping in which each limiting state is assigned a unique RGB channel: red for 1C, green for 2C, and blue for 3C turbulence.

In this work, we use a similar approach as shown by Fard Afshar et al. [6] to investigate the turbulence anisotropy of a transonic compressor stage at mid-span.

Loss estimation

According to [23] there are many different definitions of loss coefficient in regular use for individual blade rows. Perhaps the most common is the stagnation pressure loss coefficient defined for a compressor blade cascade by:

$$\zeta = \frac{p_{t1} - p_{t2}}{p_{t1} - p_1} \quad (4)$$

To better understand the loss generation in turbomachinery flows, the flow can be broken down using Denton's loss breakdown analysis [23]. The analysis is based on the application of an energy, mass and momentum balance over a control volume that includes the blade passage at the trailing edge. Although somewhat idealized, such an analysis provides an insight into the processes responsible for the resulting losses.

Albeit being able to divide the loss into different terms related to physical mechanisms, understanding these mechanisms is crucial to benefit from the loss decomposition. Therefore, to gain more detailed knowledge of the incurred losses we will be use an entropy generation-based analysis. The applied entropy analysis proposed by [24] is based on the thermodynamic entropy balance equation

$$G_s = \frac{\partial(\rho s)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial F_i}{\partial x_i} \geq 0. \quad (5)$$

The test case considered in this study has previously been investigated by Borcharding et al. [10, 11] through the application of loss decomposition. Building on this foundation, the present work specifically examines the influence of anisotropy prediction accuracy on the outcomes reported in these studies.

MAIN RESULTS

First, a synthesis of the findings and insights reported in previous studies [7, 8, 25, 10, 9] is provided to establish the current state of knowledge regarding the applied transonic compressor testcase.

General flow behavior and previous results

The general flow topology obtained with the different methods and models, as illustrated in Figure 2, can be summarized as follows. Owing to the high relative velocity, the rotor is subjected to a supersonic flow regime characterized by pronounced shock–boundary-layer interaction on the suction side of the rotor cascade. Under the relatively low inflow turbulence level considered, a laminar boundary layer develops on the suction side and undergoes transition to turbulence via a shock-induced laminar separation bubble. As demonstrated in [7], increasing the inflow turbulence likewise results in a laminar boundary layer with shock-induced transition; however, the higher turbulence intensity leads to an almost complete suppression of the separation bubble. The stator flow is dominated by rotor–stator interaction, giving rise to a wake-induced transition on the suction side, where elevated turbulence levels have no appreciable effect on either the location or the mode of the transition. This change in turbulence level increases rotor losses due to stronger shocks, leading to an overall stage loss increase of approximately 23% compared to laminar inflow.

In addition, the axial gap size was found to influence performance: reducing the rotor/stator gap decreased total losses by about 2.5%, primarily due to a 15% reduction in stator losses, while rotor losses—which account for roughly 85% of the total—remained nearly unaffected [8]. Spectral analyses further revealed strong couplings between the inflow, shock system, and separation bubble, with indications of a feedback mechanism in which separation-bubble unsteadiness convects downstream, scatters at the trailing edge, and generates upstream-propagating acoustic waves that re-excite the shock–boundary-layer interaction [25].

In Möller et al. [9], a transitional DDES framework was developed for both the original three-dimensional rotating test case and the quasi-three-dimensional (Q3D) translational configuration employed in the present study. Compared to RANS and URANS, DDES exhibited closer agreement with LES data for the Q3D configuration. Nevertheless, the wake-induced transition on the stator suction side highlighted limitations of the method, as DDES predicted a separation-induced transition that was neither captured by RANS and URANS nor observed in LES.

Entropy-based loss analysis applied in [10] identified the shock–boundary-layer interaction and the rotor suction-side boundary layer or turbulence production and mean-flow viscous dissipation respectively as the dominant contributors to aerodynamic losses. In a recent paper from Borcharding et al. [11] the entropy analysis was extended to instantaneous snapshots. While overall stage losses from time- and phase-averaged data agree, notable differ-

(a) Wall-resolved LES [8]

(b) Hybrid RANS/LES [9]

(c) URANS

FIGURE 2: INSTANTANEOUS COMPRESSOR STAGE VISUALIZATION USING SPANWISE VELOCITY ISOSURFACES AND DENSITY VARIATION ON THE SPANWISE PLANE.

ences arise in the rotor/stator loss split due to turbulence. Shock–boundary-layer interaction on the rotor suction side

is identified still as the main loss source, whereas stator losses are primarily driven by rotor wakes.

Anisotropy of turbulence

Fig. 3 shows a contour plot of the time averaged anisotropy of turbulence colored with barycentric weighted RGB for the wall-resolved LES used here. For the tur-

FIGURE 3: CONTOUR PLOT OF TIME AVERAGED ANISOTROPY OF TURBULENCE COLORED WITH BARYCENTRIC WEIGHTED RGB.

bulent inflow case shown here, it is observed that the turbulence resides in a state between isotropic (3C) and two-component (2C) turbulence in front of the rotor. Notably, at the leading edge shock upstream of the supersonic region and at the compression shock, turbulence becomes strongly anisotropic. Within the shock front, intense fluctuations are concentrated in a single direction, while the other components are only weakly affected. A similarly elevated level of anisotropy is found in the rotor and stator wakes, where the pronounced streamwise orientation of the flow produces fluctuations that are significantly stronger in one direction. Furthermore, strong velocity gradients between the wake and the surrounding high-speed flow generate directional shear stresses, thereby amplifying turbulence preferentially in certain directions. The anisotropy induced by the rotor wake is clearly reflected in the increased anisotropy of the stator inflow. This becomes particularly evident in the time-averaged representation here. Given that the dominant rotor losses originate on the suction side through shock–boundary-layer interaction [10], the rotor is examined in greater detail for suction and pressure side separately. For both sides, wall-normal lines (Red lines in Fig. 4) are introduced along which turbulence anisotropy and Reynolds stresses are systematically evaluated.

FIGURE 4: CONTOUR PLOT OF TIME AVERAGED ANISOTROPY OF TURBULENCE COLORED WITH BARYCENTRIC WEIGHTED RGB (ZOOM ON ROTOR).

Rotor suction side To gain further insight into the state of turbulence, Fig. 5 shows the Reynolds stresses along the rotor suction side, normalized by the axial velocity u_1 at the compressor inlet. It is clear that the shear stresses $\overline{u'w'}$ and $\overline{v'w'}$ are negligible compared to the other Reynolds stress components. This behavior can be attributed to the two-dimensional nature of the underlying test case and the isotropic specification of the turbulent inflow. Consequently, the following analysis focuses on the remaining Reynolds stresses. Notably, the shear stress $\overline{u'v'}$ attains magnitudes comparable to those of the normal stresses, both within the shock and in the downstream boundary layer. This observation is consistent with previous findings, such as those reported by Fard Afshar et al. [6].

In the region of the leading-edge shock, only the normal stress $\overline{u'u'}$ and the shear stress $\overline{u'v'}$ are of significance, while $\overline{v'v'}$ remains roughly an order of magnitude smaller. Interestingly, within the compression shock, the stresses $\overline{u'u'}$ and $\overline{v'v'}$ appear to reach similar magnitudes to $\overline{u'v'}$. The third component, $\overline{w'w'}$, is relevant only within the boundary layer.

Upstream of shock To obtain a quantitative assessment of the individual Reynolds stresses, their distribution with respect to turbulence anisotropy, and their evolution within the suction-side boundary layer from the leading to the shock-boundary layer interaction, Figure 6 presents the in-

FIGURE 5: REYNOLDS STRESSES ALONG THE ROTOR SUCTION SIDE.

dividual Reynolds stress components together with the resulting turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) at two axial positions. The boundary-layer edge is indicated by a dashed black line.

At the first position near the leading edge, significant stress contributions can be observed not only within the boundary layer but also outside of it. These are attributed to the leading-edge shock and the supersonic region. Of particular interest is the composition of the individual components: in this region, the third normal component, $\overline{w'w'}$, exhibits a substantially larger contribution compared to $\overline{u'u'}$, $\overline{v'v'}$, and $\overline{u'v'}$, and thus represents the dominant contribution to the resulting turbulent kinetic energy in this area.

Within the boundary layer, a more expected behavior is

observed, where $\overline{u'u'}$, $\overline{v'v'}$, and $\overline{u'v'}$ contribute most prominently to the TKE. This trend persists further downstream, toward the compression shock at $s/s_{max} = 0.15$. Here, the contributions outside the boundary layer are almost negligible, and within the boundary layer, only $\overline{u'u'}$, $\overline{v'v'}$, and $\overline{u'v'}$ play a significant role.

FIGURE 6: REYNOLDS STRESSES (LINES) AND CORRESPONDING COMPONENT OF REYNOLDS STRESS ANISOTROPY TENSOR (COLOR BARS) ALONG WALL NORMAL LINES.

The turbulence structure can be further inferred from the color bars shown on the right-hand side of Figure 6 and

(a) $s/s_{max} = 0.04$

(b) $s/s_{max} = 0.15$

FIGURE 7: LUMLEY-TRIANGLE ALONG WALL NORMAL LINES.

is represented for each axial position as a trajectory within the Lumley triangle in Figure 7. In the vicinity of the leading edge, the turbulence exhibits an initially strongly isotropic three-component (3C) state outside the boundary layer, which progressively transitions through a two-component (2C) state near the boundary-layer edge toward a one-component (1C) limiting state within the boundary layer.

Further downstream, a similar evolution is observed; however, the intermediate 2C state becomes less distinct, and the turbulence undergoes a more rapid collapse toward the 1C state.

Downstream of shock Downstream of the compression shock, a different distribution and composition of the individual Reynolds stress components can be observed, as illustrated in Figure 8 for two axial positions. The first position is located just downstream of the shock-boundary-

(a) $s/s_{max} = 0.25$

(b) $s/s_{max} = 0.95$

FIGURE 8: REYNOLDS STRESSES (LINES) AND CORRESPONDING COMPONENTIAL OF REYNOLDS STRESS ANISOTROPY TENSOR (COLOR BARS) ALONG WALL NORMAL LINES.

(a) $s/s_{max} = 0.25$

(b) $s/s_{max} = 0.95$

FIGURE 9: LUMLEY-TRIANGLE ALONG WALL NORMAL LINES.

layer interaction, and the second one is near the trailing edge.

Immediately downstream of the shock–boundary-layer interaction, the $\overline{u'u'}$ component exhibits the largest contribution. The $\overline{w'w'}$ component also shows a significantly higher magnitude compared to the results in Figure 6, reaching values comparable to those of $\overline{v'v'}$ and $\overline{u'v'}$. More-

over, the shape of the profiles within the boundary layer changes noticeably. While in Figure 6 the distributions resembled a normal-like profile with a distinct peak at the center of the boundary layer, the profiles at this location—except for $\overline{u'u'}$ —tend to develop two peaks, resulting in a fuller boundary-layer shape.

Further downstream, toward the trailing edge, the behavior of the components changes again. The contribution of $\overline{w'w'}$ appears to decrease, while $\overline{u'u'}$ remains dominant. Together with $\overline{v'v'}$ and $\overline{u'v'}$, the profile shape gradually returns to a single pronounced peak that shifts toward the rotor wall.

Downstream of the compression shock, the turbulence structure changes accordingly, as shown in Figure 9. Immediately downstream of the shock–boundary-layer interaction, the turbulence outside the boundary layer again exhibits a strongly isotropic three-component (3C) character, which transitions directly into a two-component (2C) state within the boundary layer. Further downstream along the boundary layer, this behavior evolves such that the initially 3C state passes through a one-component (1C) state and gradually approaches a two-component (2C) configuration near the rotor surface.

Rotor pressure side The boundary layer on the pressure side is likewise characterized by the Reynolds stress components $\overline{u'u'}$, $\overline{v'v'}$, $\overline{w'w'}$, and $\overline{u'v'}$, whereas $\overline{u'w'}$ and $\overline{v'w'}$ do not contribute significantly. Figure 10 presents the distributions of the Reynolds stresses and the turbulent kinetic energy at positions near the leading and trailing edges. Near the leading edge, the qualitative behavior resembles that observed on the suction side, while the profiles near the trailing edge also show similar trends to those on the suction side in the corresponding region.

However, on the pressure side, the $\overline{v'v'}$ and $\overline{w'w'}$ components appear to contribute more strongly near the leading edge than on the suction side. Near the trailing edge, the pressure-side behavior becomes more comparable to that of the suction side, although the $\overline{v'v'}$ component still exhibits a larger contribution than $\overline{u'u'}$.

The turbulence structure on the pressure side can again be interpreted using the Lumley triangle in Figure 11. Near the leading edge, the turbulence exhibits an isotropic three-component (3C) state outside the boundary layer, which transitions first toward a one-component (1C) state and subsequently toward a two-component (2C) state close to the surface. On the suction side, this sequence was only observed downstream of the shock–boundary-layer interaction. The evolution of the turbulence structure near the trailing edge is very similar to that on the suction side, where the initially isotropic 3C character transitions

through a 1C state and approaches the 2C state near the wall.

(a) $s/s_{max} = 0.04$

(b) $s/s_{max} = 0.95$

FIGURE 10: REYNOLDS STRESSES (LINES) AND CORRESPONDING COMPONENTIAL OF REYNOLDS STRESS ANISOTROPY TENSOR (COLOR BARS) ALONG WALL NORMAL LINES.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

As outlined in the introduction, the dominant sources of aerodynamic losses at the stage level are the shock–boundary-layer interaction on the rotor suction side

(a) $s/s_{max} = 0.04$

(b) $s/s_{max} = 0.95$

FIGURE 11: LUMLEY-TRIANGLE ALONG WALL NORMAL LINES.

and the wake–boundary-layer interaction on the stator suction side. In a more detailed consideration of the rotor, however, not only the mixing losses in the wake but also the behavior of the boundary layer on the pressure side must be taken into account. This has been explicitly demonstrated in the work of Borchering et al. [10, 11].

For both the suction and pressure sides of the ro-

tor, a distinctly anisotropic character of the turbulence is observed, which cannot be adequately represented by the conventional linear eddy-viscosity-based turbulence and transition models. Beyond this, the varying turbulence structures—manifesting as one-, two-, and three-component (1C, 2C, and 3C) states within the boundary layer, both in the wall-normal and streamwise directions—introduce additional complexity. It is further evident that the Reynolds stress component $\overline{u'v'}$ makes a substantial contribution not only within the boundary layer but also, in this particular case, within the shock–boundary-layer interaction region, encompassing both the compression shock and the local supersonic flow field.

Accordingly, both qualitative and quantitative loss predictions must account for the differing and, in part, highly anisotropic contributions of the individual Reynolds stress components—an aspect that is not captured by standard RANS closures. It therefore remains an open question whether the use of more sophisticated Reynolds stress models or hybrid RANS–LES methodologies can provide a computationally efficient yet physically accurate alternative for predicting such complex flow phenomena.

In this study, a detailed evaluation of turbulence anisotropy and its behavior has been presented based on a wall-resolved Large Eddy Simulation of a transonic rotor midspan section. Building on previous investigations of the same test case, in which a comprehensive entropy loss decomposition was conducted, the rotor suction side—where shock–boundary-layer interaction occurs—was identified as a major source of entropy losses.

The corresponding analyses of the Reynolds stress distribution, the resulting turbulent kinetic energy, and the turbulence structure characterized via the Lumley triangle reveal a pronounced deviation from isotropic turbulence. Such anisotropy fundamentally challenges the assumptions underlying conventional linear eddy-viscosity turbulence and transition models that are widely employed in both industry and research.

The insights gained from this study will serve as the foundation for future investigations aimed at assessing the impact of turbulence anisotropy modeling accuracy on loss prediction. To this end, additional numerical simulations of reduced fidelity—such as unsteady and steady RANS computations employing various turbulence closure formulations—will be performed and evaluated with respect to their capability to reproduce turbulence anisotropy and corresponding loss behavior. Furthermore, the influence of the accuracy of anisotropy prediction on the overall loss generation will be systematically examined.

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